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ORNAMENT AS A DOMINANT TENDENCY OF HOUSEHOLD PRODUCT DESIGN IN KOREA

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ABSTRACT

One of the extraordinary phenomena of product design in Korea lately is ornamental tendency and its surface treatment. It is curious why industrial design, which traditionally has posed as a favorite of machine aesthetics, is interested in decoration and even tries to resemble works of art. Of course, it is certain that this must be a solution of emotional marketing to artificially create a new demand by breaking through the saturated market. However, this may not be accurate as an answer to “why ornaments, especially surface ones?” Probably, surface ornaments are the content or substance that implies a cultural archetype that can be caught from the base of the Korean design phenomenon. This paper proposes a deductive supposition that at the very point which is difficult to grasp by the epistemic frame of dominant discourse, the ‘grammar of ornament’ manifested in the history of western design, the DNA of Korean design will be revealed.

Keywords: Ornament, Product Design, Korea.

INTRODUCTION

During recent years in Korea, the ornamental tendency is dominant especially in the household product design industry, which has taken the initiative in the aesthetics of Modernism due to its ideologies. It is true that this inclination was led by the industry itself in order to overcome chronic depression in domestic demands. In addition, since postmodernism and the advent of the emotional design, ornament has made its position acknowledged in terms of design theories, and its due value has already been acknowledged. It is not satisfactory, however, to interpret reincarnation of

decoration a mere aspect of marketing or to think it as a theoretical intention. To analyze it in the aspect of marketing is to open it to other alternatives, not only an emphasis on ornamentation, which can be too vague to be an answer. It is necessary to understand the current ornamentalism in Korea as a potential for intrinsic values to be found rather than ignore it as a temporary trend.

This proposal starts from the deductive premise or hypothesis that a decorative trait connotes authentic Korean design contents that can be disclosed from the particular scene of Korean cultures and histories. The paper is going to be composed of five parts including the introduction. In the second part, following the introduction, the wide-spreading examples of ornamental trends in product design, especially household product or home appliance design in Korea and their socio-cultural backgrounds will be investigated.

The third part will examine the rich heritages of ornament that has been handed down in the western design history, covering eclecticism in the 19th century, Art Nouveau around the turn of the century, Art Deco, Pop Design, Anti-design, and postmodernism in the 20th century. Through this course, we will pay attention to an inevitable tension that has continuously existed between ornament and anti-ornament, and to the fact that ornamental property has been denied or approved as a denotation of resistance against the dominant bourgeois middle-class ideologies whatever it is modernism or postmodernism.

The fourth part will infer that even if western design and Korean design looks similar in terms of decorative expression, they are basically different because the tension and the resistance, which were discussed in the third part, are not found in the ornamental tendency of Korean design, or are very

Figure 1. A strategic exhibition with the title of 'LG Air Conditioner Meet 6 Artists' was held at the gallery in Seoul. Under the concept of 'Meeting of fine art and product Design,' renowned 6 artists designed the new model of 2008 year standing air conditioner. Customers could purchase the new series of LG 'Art Dios' product at the gallery if they want. They were coined as 'Art appliance' or 'Interior objet' by LG Company.

loose if they exist. In Korea, ornament is neither a symbol of a 'crime', a 'grammar', nor sub-cultural 'resistance', but an unbiased, pure decoration itself so to speak. In consideration of the past socio-economic milieu of Korean design, it can be said that design, whether the modern design or the postmodern design, has been regarded simply as an agency that creates 'surplus values', not a representative of human freedom per se. Finally, the paper will conclude that unlike the western design, an ideological defensive system against ornament has existed because of the short design history of Korea, and this implies, ironically, the crucial point that reveals Korean design's own cultural attributes without any prejudice. Furthermore, it will propose that appropriate moment to establish a Korean design identity is during the current period since Korean design has gained some kind of self-confidence after all.

THE ORNAMENT OF PRODUCT DESIGN IN KOREA AND THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC BACKGROUND

Since a few years ago, artistic design, surpassing craft work, which paints splendid colors or

luxuriously decorates the surface of product design -- especially home appliances-- with elegant floral patterns or even with Swarovski jewelry and mother-of-pearl, has been in vogue. Although the degree to which this takes place has reduced now, still many kinds of product design such as, refrigerators, Kimchi refrigerators, washing machines, laundry dryers, air conditioners, dishwashers, oven ranges, microwave ovens, humidifiers, water purifiers, air purifiers, gas stoves, rice cookers, strong boxes, computers, mobile phones, MP3, cosmetics containers, china and so on aim at ornamentalization, emotionalization, fashionization, artification and luxuriation as if they are competing with each other. As the need of consumers who want to show their own individuality and tastes become stronger, the phase in which artistic design leads trend is, in fact, a global phenomenon. In so-called star designers, the course of designing sculptural objects of which functions cannot be perceived at a glance reflects this tendency. As a result, more and more artists or fashion designers, not product designers, participate in the process of designing the external features of

Figure 2. Advertisement from LG 'Light-wave oven' catalogue. The surface of oven is adorned with graceful floral patterns and it says "Your husband shall come home early as fast as light - 'Dios light-wave oven'" The images of oven and wife are identical in the sense of ornateness and loveliness. It implies that both are attractive enough to seduce her spouse into home.

the product. To differentiate products, enterprises enter into strategic partnerships with them.¹ The socio-economic background behind the ornamental product design that insists on "emotional luxury goods" or "luxury home appliances"² is closely related to the increase in the purchasing power of women. Now women have become key decision-makers who are the subjects of design choice and take responsibilities for purchases at home.³ Thus, the ornamental tendency of product design in Korea focuses on a marketing strategy that considers female consumers and aims at the basic psychology of Korean housewives who are boastful of enormous

power in the consumer market, especially with regard household products. It is natural that "to say like Freud, ornament can be seen as a symptom related to the return of the repressed. . . ." since "ornamental expressions are interpreted as a means of realization of their repressed egos for women whose social activities are limited unlike men in the home area which is permitted as their domain through the release of ornament energy."⁴ One of the important ideologies of the design of home electric appliances, that is, electrical products for the home, is to erase the trace of domestic labors as much as possible. The most ideal image of home appliances is to inject the fantasy which makes housewives believe that they have been liberated from a yoke imposed on them traditionally and that they can enjoy leisure for rest and culture 'without dripping a drop of water in their hands.'⁵ Logically, the image of home appliances suitable for home use, not industrial use, has to have more furniture image than machine image. If the surface of a home appliance looks as elegant as that of luxurious furniture and looks as beautiful as jewelry decorations, like the slogan of the 2008 SAMSUNG Electronics home appliances household product,

¹ So called 'Techart Marketing' technique is this. Techart marketing, a coined word of Technology and Art is a marketing trend that tries to reinforce premium brand image that satisfy even consumers' emotions in addition to mention functionality by reflecting the works of famous artists or star designers on product design.

² "Andre Kim's luxury home appliances astonish the world. SAMSUNG Electronics covered art on home appliances. . . . A person concerned with SAMSUNG Electronics said, "We found an answer while looking for a luxury concept of premium appliances differentiated in emotional technologies and design. The home appliances Andre Kim, a top designer in this age, will lead the age of artistic home appliances with high quality and sensitivity while continuing with air conditioner and oven range, etc. in the future." (Source: International Textile News, www.itnk.co.kr/d01.htm?mode=body&page=5&number=&key=&category=)

³ It is said that about 90% of home purchase are decided by housewives.

⁴ Young-lan Ko (2004), "Toward the Cultural Approach to the Discipline of Korean Design History: A Plea for the Domestic Handcrafts of Yang, Gap-jo," *Journal of Korean Society of Design Science*, vol.17, no.4, p.381.

⁵ Adrian Forty (1986), *Objects of Desire: Design and Society Since 1750*, trans. Bo-yun Heo (2004), Seoul: Ilbit Publishing Co., pp. 119-150.

Figure 3. Various kind of decorative patterns shown in 'The Grammar of Ornament' written by Owen Jones. It is not too much to say that 'History of human being is that of ornament' since decorative design is alive in all of us regardless of time, culture, or history.

there is no reason why it cannot rise to the rank of luxury home appliances as “an interior *objet*” that can decorate “the living room beautifully in the look of furniture.”

THE HISTORY OF WESTERN DESIGN AND THE LEGACY OF ORNAMENTALISM

Like it is not too much to say that ‘history of human being is that of ornament,’ since the beginning of history, the human race have been able to overcome the absurdity of life and to find the wisdom to live a transient life abundantly by granting, communicating and sharing meanings to a trivial everyday life through the symbolism of ornament.⁶ Then, is history of modern design anti-ornamentalism as known to the world? As we know, modern design movement attempted to reconstruct the chaotic reality brought out by the new industrial civilization to the rational world by giving a new order of geometric forms based on so-called functionalism, and regarded ornamentalism and historicism in the 19th century eclectic design as a redundant, regressive heritage of the old age to get over. However, to track the actual developmental process of design history, there is a paradox that ornament which modernism felt uncomfortable ideologically under the justification of functionality, rationality and

economic efficiency, has continued to be summoned.⁷

From as early as Pre-Raphaelite, Arts and Crafts Movement or Art Nouveau to Art Deco which overlaps with the age when modernistic visual grammar emerged, organic modernism, post-WWII pop design or anti-design, the variables of ornament has never been forced out from the grammar of modern design. The legitimate status of ornament was acknowledged both theoretically and methodologically since the emergence of postmodernism and human sensibility ergonomics. As you can see that in the phenomenon in which not only post-modernism or deconstructivism but also neo-orientalism or artistic and authorial design are emerging, it is not too much to say that now ornament has been completely reinstated kicking away its negative shadow which has been formed through the ideological prism, modernism. Compared to the chronology of ornamentalism, the history of American proto-functionalism or Russian Constructivism, which pursued anti-ornamental and anti-historic ideology, or the propagandist functionalism spreaded from the design education of Bauhaus and Ulm School of Design feels relatively poor.

⁶ Owen Jones (2001), *The Grammar of Ornament*, Paris, L'Aventurine (Originally published by Bernard Quaritch in 1910).

⁷ Durant classifies even modernism as a decorative style with a particular visual language. Stuart Durant (1986), *Ornament: From the Industrial Revolution to Today*, New York, The Overlook Press, pp. 263-288.

ORNAMENT AND KOREAN DESIGN DNA

The legacy of ornamentalism handed down continuously in the history of modern design results from the tight ideological tension which has existed between ornamentalism and anti-ornamentalism. No matter whether it is modernism, post-modernism, *avant-garde* or kitsch, it is worth noting that decoration has been denied or supported as a meaning of a kind of resistance against dominant bourgeois middle-class culture.⁸ Recent cultural phenomenon of the domestic and the global in which design and art encounter each other through ornamental vocabulary may look the same on the superficial level. However, tension and resistance between ornamentalism and functionalism found in the history of Western design is not found in Korean ornament or even if so, it is loose, so there is a fundamental difference between the attitude of recognition of Western design and that of Korean design toward ornament. In this sense, to generalize the reincarnation of surface ornamentalism in Korea which even looks unconventional and the explosive response in the market to it as a successful case of

Figure 4. LG 'Art Dios' refrigerator (Left). SAMSUNG Kim-chi refrigerator (Right) designed by late Andre Kim, a top fashion designers in Korea Both products represent luxurious 'Art appliance' with premium quality.

⁸ Matei Calinescu (1987), *Five Faces of Modernity: Modernism, Avant-garde, Decadence, Kitsch, Postmodernism*, trans. Young-uk Lee et al. (1993), Seoul: Vision and Language Publishing Co.

emotional design process⁹ or to be covered under the global trend is likely to remain superficial, stereotypical understanding that overlook the particularity of Korean design. Then it may be the time when in addition to approaching the ornamental tendency of recent product design in Korea from a producer's position, a review on ornament as the cultural identity of Korean design from another angle is necessary.

Ornament in Korea is not a 'crime,' 'grammar' or 'symbol' of sub-cultural resistance but rather a decoration itself as a pure 'signifier.' Judging from the domestic socio-economic milieu until now, modern design has been recognized as the magic flute that produces surplus value before the substitute of liberation. At the very point where the dialectical framework of recognition that the modern discourse of Western design on ornament implies does not operate, you may discover the DNA of Korean design --with a unique double helical structure where particularity and universality cross each other-- which rushes toward pure desire for decoration without any ideological bias.¹⁰ When we look at the decorative disposition of purchasers without any prejudice, in other words, by acknowledging 'effective histories'¹¹ in a Foucaultian stance which has been neglected from the perspective of production until now, the identity of Korean design will arise to the surface. For example, the late Andre Kim, a fashion designer was able to occupy a unique territory in drawing a topographical map of Korean pop culture since he

⁹ Un-hyoung Kim, Hee-chang Lee (2008), "A Case Study of Emotional Design and Design Process," *Industrial Design*, Vol.1, No.1, pp.19-25.

¹⁰ I do not expect other researchers easily sympathize the presenter's paradoxical argument. This is because designers or artists who see the product design trend that focuses on surface ornamentation negatively as follows may be much more. "I think there is too much design around use. Everything has design, and the design is attached like superfluous one not melt with things mostly. People seem to think design to be make-up on the surface of things." (Gyu-cheol Ahn)" Requoted in Myoung-hwan Kim (2005), *Art & Design: Extension of Design Concept*, Design Locus Publishing Co., p.22.

¹¹ Gi-bong Kim (2000), "'Hard' Modernity and 'Soft' Modernity," *History & Culture*, Vol.1, p.161.

spent his whole life practicing so-called 'theory of fantastic design' which insisted on inspiring aristocratic nobility and future-oriented emotions of sophistication not only in fashion but also in lifestyle itself in spite of mocking glances of many people. Now, interestingly enough no one depreciates his design calling it kitsch, instead it becomes one of the Korea's top brands. Above all, he is remembered as a national yet friendly icon. If one rebukes his design as kitsch even if the premium home appliances, interior space and china, etc. of which design was commissioned to him got excellent results, it may not be different from ridiculing the taste of ordinary people who recognize his design as a luxury good and purchase it with reverence.¹²

IMPLICATIONS

Until now, there was a tendency in the field of Korean design to try to find its identity in extra-design elements such as industry, science, technology, engineering, economics and marketing. If surface ornament, artistry, or a rich sensibility for fashionableness is the spiral that forms one axis of Korean design DNA, the social, psychological collective energy toward ornament must not be restrained or hidden. Instead, cultivating new

confidence and sensibility for Korean ornamental aesthetics more minutely and generating internationally differentiated, and yet globally universal design grammar of Korea is the task. For this, firstly the weight of design education must be attached to the restoration of artistic abilities. Excessive subdivision and specialization of design education may wither Korean design DNA. As you see in the fact that recently product and interior design markets are expanded and reproduced centering around artistic design, the boundaries between product design and interior design, installation art and architectural design, graphic design and painting, or image design and fashion design are being taken down in reality. By offering interdisciplinary curricula with which students can work on integrated projects in which there are no distinction between design and art, the artistic inner abilities of prospective designers could be intensified more. The very fact that ideological defense mechanism against ornament has not been formulated yet unlike the West is, paradoxically, the source of power that enables Korean design to generate their own design identity spontaneously. It may be a sound phenomenon that the collective unconscious of culture arises to the surface and reveal a certain pattern --even if it is ornament.

Figure 5. Collection of Kim-chi refrigerators with various surface decoration designed by DIMCHAI brand. Dimchai treats Kim-chi refrigerator as an art-piece. Under the catch phrase of "Enjoy the Culture with DIMCHAI," it aims for bringing back Korean culture into Kim-chi refrigerator.

¹² Since the concept of Kitsch itself is a dichotomous enunciation act presupposes the concept of high and low tastes, the term, *kitsch* should be used more carefully than for now. Catherine McDermott (1994), *Essential Design*, London, Bloomsbury Publishing, p.139.

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